

5.1

Capacity building program, scripts, material

Contact us

info@biasproject.eu
www.biasproject.eu

LOBA[®]

farplas

@BIASProjectEU

D5.1

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Main Author(s)

Name	Organisation
Maria Sangiuliano	SVEN
Maria Giovanna Zamburlini	SVEN

Peer Reviews

Name	Organisation
Carlotta Rigotti	ULEID
Silvia Ecclesia	NTNU

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Partner abbreviations

Full name

NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway)
HI	Háskóli Íslands (University of Iceland)
LOBA	Loba (Portugal)
CHX	Crowd Helix (Ireland)
SVEN	Smart Venice (Italy)
DIGI	Digiotouch (Estonia)
ULEID	Leiden University (The Netherlands)
FARPL	Farplas Automotive (Türkiye)
BFH	Bern University of Applied Sciences (Switzerland)

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AbbreviationsMeaning

1. AI: Artificial Intelligence
2. AIA: Artificial Intelligence Act
3. AIF: Italian Association of Trainers
4. ALTAI: Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
5. CBR: Case Based Reasoning
6. CPDP - Computers, Privacy and Data Protection
7. CSO: Civil Society Organizations
8. ETUI: European Trade Union Institute
9. GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation
10. GE: Gender Equality
11. HR: Human Resources
12. MOOC: Massive Open Online Courses
13. NGOs: Non-Governmental Organisations
14. NLP: Natural Language Processing
15. TU: Trade Unions
16. VSD: Value Sensitive Design
17. WEAT: Word Embedding Association Test

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1 Introduction

This deliverable is part of Work package (WP5) – Capacity building and raising awareness for Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Human Resources (HR) community, and its Task 5.2 “Capacity building design and development”. As capacity building plays an important part in the BIAS project Impact strategy, the deliverable describes the thorough articulation of the process that led to the design of the training courses, including the initial mapping and learning needs assessment efforts part of Task 5.1 “Learning needs analysis for different beneficiaries”.

The report also collects the programmes, scripts, and materials designed for the courses along with monitoring tools, developed during the first iteration of the capacity building program during the initial pilot test (M20-21) and the first roll-out phases (M28–30), identified under Task 5.3 “Capacity building roll-out and evaluation”.

The second phase of the Task 5.3 will be the main subject of D5.3 “Capacity building evaluation methodology and final report” due in M46, including: the evaluation of the first edition and the redesign/adjustment of the courses as well as the evaluation of the second edition of the programme implemented between M36–38.

2 Executive summary

The report highlights how the capacity building programme was tailored to different target groups, as the initial plans to mostly address the courses to AI specialists and HR professionals were adapted and changed to include Trade Unions (TU) and Civil Society Organisations (CSO)/Non-governmental organisations (NGOs). In view of rolling out the two editions of the programme, a pilot testing of the course for HR officials took place M20 (June 2024), and its results are reported as well in this document, leading to revised duration of the course and adaptations/improvements of the content/methods as well.

Furthermore, this deliverable summarises the material that has been used when rolling out the BIAS capacity building programme's first edition in 6 on-site and 3 online sessions, between M28–30 (February–April 2025) aiming at engaging with 35 participants each in Estonia, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Norway, The Netherlands, Portugal, Switzerland, Türkiye.

The communication materials/outlets designed to reach out to the different target groups is also described, given the importance of engagement efforts to collect registrations to the courses.

Smart Venice (SVEN) coordinated the development of the training contents and materials with the contribution of the multidisciplinary scholars and experts inside the consortium and external experts from the Advisory Board. SVEN was also in charge of delivering the training courses, prior to an internal "Train the trainers" session. LOBA (WP7) closely supported the design and development of the capacity building dissemination materials and the management of communications on social media. Individual partners acted as hosting organizations for the courses.

What is emerging from the report is a high-quality capacity building programme distilling the knowledge generated from the BIAS consortium into accessible and actionable content for professionals working with AI, and for individuals and organisations who could be impacted by AI-driven discrimination. The deliverable makes all materials accessible is aimed at facilitating replication and exploitation in different contexts.

D5.1 is structured in the following sections:

1. Introduction and executive summary.
2. Design of the courses: summarising the process of designing the sessions based on a need assessment analysis/background information, and the results of the pilot test session.
3. The target audiences, and the courses formats and curricula as well as methodological approach.
4. Trainers' teams: identifying the trainers' profiles, describing their roles in the preparation and facilitation of the classes.
5. Evaluation tools and processes: describing the format and structure of the evaluating tools filled in by trainers after each capacity building session.
6. Conclusive remarks.
7. Annexes: providing links to the materials produced in view of replication and impact.
8. References.

3 Design of the courses

3.1 Overview of the learning needs analysis and design process

The definition of the capacity building content came through an iterative approach through multiple workshops involving partners, ensuring input from research activities, the project Advisory Board, and inspiration from sister projects, as well as external experts. This process helped identifying both transversal objectives to the capacity building programme and specific ones to the three final target audiences (AI experts, HR specialists and Workers Representatives/NGOs).

In the frame of T5.1 between December 2022 (M16) and December 2023 (M26), SVEN conducted a learning needs analysis, preparatory to the capacity-building programme, articulated in several steps:

1. This first activity was structured in 3 sub-activities:
 - The identification of the different professional's profiles to be involved in the capacity-building process.
 - The integration of ad hoc questions in the interview structure within T2.3 "Needs assessment expert interviews" led by HI and conducted by WP2 Consortium partners, targeting HR professionals and AI specialist¹.
 - The organization of a dedicated brainstorming session within the international co-creation workshop taking place in Venice on the 7th of December 2023².
2. Initial benchmarking of existing courses and brainstorming with consortium partners. Initial involvement and input from partners covering AI (BFH and NTNU) and HR (FARPLAS).
3. Redefining phase:
 - Additional contributions from partners during project meetings.
 - Pilot test Pilot testing to refine design in June 2024.

In addition, the training principles applied within the H2020 GE Academy Project offered a transversal approach methodological point of view to the design process. The outcome was the definition of the learning objectives for 3 targeted professionals' profiles in the BIAS capacity-building programme (AI experts, HR specialists, Workers Representatives/NGOs).

It is worth to mention here additional inputs that have been nourishing the capacity building program:

- Training expert consultation (AIF, Italian Association of Trainers): with focus on HR professionals, consulted on 10th April 2024, during a dedicated workshop organised by SVEN, where the preliminary idea of introducing human-machine interaction in the training programme itself was tested and validated.
- Advisory Board members involvement: the BIAS Advisory Board members contributed to an online session on 18 November 2025 to the definition of key communication messages targeting each of the 3 profiles of professionals to be involved in the capacity-building process. They supported the identification of key channels/networks to promote the programme and provided input on learning needs and specific methodologies for workers representatives and NGOs, thanks to the presence in the Board of Aida Ponce del Castillo, senior researcher at the ETUI (European Trade Unions Institute). Connection with and learning from sisters' projects: such as the FINDHR³ project whose e-learning programme was attended by SVEN.

¹ For details, please see Deliverable D2.1 "Preliminary Holistic report on mapping, survey, interviews" for further details.

² For details, please see Deliverable D2.1 "Preliminary Holistic report on mapping, survey, interviews" for further details.

³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101070212>

- Special contribution and feedback loop with partners to tap in specific knowledge and research outcomes, from:
 - BFH for the content development of the course targeting AI specialists and the input part on AI models.
 - NTNU for input on case studies from the ethnographic research for the course for Trade Unions and NGOs.
 - ULEID for the input part on the AI Act and the General Data Protection Regulation.

3.2 Learning needs analysis and design process: methodology and results

3.2.1 Learning needs: ad hoc and interviews questions & dedicated brainstorming

Methodology

As previously mentioned, SVEN conducted an initial learning needs analysis preparatory to the capacity-building programme design and the identification of its targets.

This first activity was structured in 3 sub-activities:

1. The identification of the different profiles of professionals to be involved in the capacity-building process, mainly conducted through internal brainstorming with consortium partners.
2. The integration of ad hoc questions in the interview structure within T2.3.
3. The organization of a dedicated brainstorming within the international co-creation workshop taking place in Venice on the 7th of December 2023.

Under the first sub-activity, an internal brainstorming took place in December 2022 among SVEN, BFH, NTNU and FARPLAS, involving partners covering AI (BFH and NTNU) and HR (FARPLAS). This was complemented with the ETUI expertise (Advisory Board member) as far as workers representatives are concerned.

In the frame of the second sub-activity, SVEN elaborated a few ad hoc questions that were integrated into the interviews' structure elaborated in the frame of T2.3, targeting AI experts and HR professionals. In particular, the following questions were formulated and integrated in the interviews:

HR professionals:

- If you were to receive training concerning bias in AI, what topics would you most want addressed?

AI experts:

- Did you attend any course about ethics in AI within your university curriculum or beyond it? Which one(s)?
- If you were to receive training concerning bias in AI, what topics would you most want addressed?

Interviews were taken in 7 partner countries (Estonia, Iceland, Italy, Netherlands, Norway, Switzerland and Türkiye) and 35 AI experts and 33 HR professionals were interviewed.

Summary of interviewees' answers on their expectations within a capacity-building programme:

Answers from HR professionals were centered on the better understanding of bias caused by AI, including its definitions, typologies, mitigation measures, etc. Thus, specifically, the mentioned topics were:

- Theoretical knowledge on bias: Understanding the philosophical and theoretical assumptions of bias, including its relationship and differences with prejudices and stereotypes.
- Definition of biases in the workplace: Emphasizing unconscious biases and their impact on decision-making processes.
- Role of AI developers: Exploring the role of AI developers in conceptualizing bias and developing mitigation tools to address biases in AI systems.
- Empirical formation with examples: Utilizing real-life examples, such as roleplays or sharing experiences, to understand the implications of bias in AI.
- Types of bias and relation to diversity: Recognizing different types of bias (e.g., name, age, background, life phases, burnout) and their relation to diversity in various contexts.
- Current state of bias detection: Examining the current state of bias detection, including examples like distinguishing between job hoppers and individuals with diverse work experiences.
- Differences between positive and negative discrimination: Understanding the distinctions between positive and negative discrimination, as well as recognizing instances where bias may lead to individuals feeling discriminated against.
- Mitigation measures: Exploring various mitigation measures, both AI-based and non-AI-based, to address biases in AI systems effectively.
- Measurement of diversity: Investigating methods for measuring diversity within AI systems and assessing the effectiveness of diversity initiatives.
- Ethical aspects and social impact of AI: Considering the ethical implications of AI and its social impact, particularly regarding bias and discrimination, and exploring ways to address these issues responsibly.

Answers from the AI experts were more related to technical aspects about bias in the technological solutions, such as identifying, preventing, and managing them:

- Different types of bias: Understanding various types of bias and providing examples of biased AI systems in dimensions such as gender, race, and class. Understanding bias implications in AI systems.
- Mechanisms generating bias: Exploring how biases are generated, including the influence of developers' stereotypes, and recognizing that technology is created by people.
- Inclusion of bias in technological development: Understanding how bias is incorporated at different stages of technological development (data collection, algorithm design, and output) and determining when it should be measured.
- Identifying and mitigating bias: Learning how to identify biased data sources and models and implementing mitigation strategies. This includes distinguishing whether algorithms are replicating existing biases or creating new ones.
- Debiasing methods: Exploring methods to debias AI systems and understanding which algorithms to use for verifying biases.
- Frameworks and regulations: Familiarizing with existing frameworks, both in terms of software and intellectual property, and understanding regulations and ethics frameworks, including European acts.
- Accountability and Transparency: Developing strategies to ensure accountability, fairness, and transparency in AI systems, including corrective measures when biases are identified.
- Debiasing services and certifications: Awareness of companies providing debiasing services or certifications for AI systems.

- Teaching about data quality and discrimination: Educating on the type and quality of data to avoid discrimination and gender stereotypes, emphasizing the importance of using unbiased data.
- Awareness in public and industries: Understanding the level of awareness of biases in both the public and industries, and strategies to raise awareness and address biases effectively.

Table 1: Summary of interviewees' answers on their expectations within a capacity-building programme

The third sub-activity consisted in a brainstorming session taking place within the international co-creation workshop held in Venice on the 7th of December 2023. In the workshop, beyond project partners, 19 external stakeholders participated. In particular: 8 HR professionals, 4 AI experts, 4 representatives of CSOs, and 3 workers' representatives. 5 mixed groups were created, and the following points were discussed:

- Existing courses/training on bias in AI or close-by topics (to feed the benchmarking activity, input included in the dedicated paragraph below).
- Knowledge/information you would expect to get from a capacity building program:
 - Fundamentals of AI and Bias:
 - Definitions and examples of different types of bias (algorithmic, societal, etc.).
 - Explanation of how AI works in recruitment (stages, Machine-Learning logic, etc.).
 - Overview of the limitations and risks of current AI systems.
 - Practical Implementation:
 - Insights into hiring systems and real-world usage of AI in recruitment.
- Skills that you would expect to develop/improve:
 - Technical/Analytical Skills:
 - Prompt engineering and AI performance evaluation.
 - Data interpretation and assessment metrics for fairness.
 - Critical Thinking and Ethical Reasoning:
 - Developing the ability to challenge AI outputs, reason critically, and exercise judgment.
 - Raising self-awareness and fostering equity-focused dialogue.
- Case studies to share (both from your organization and elsewhere):
 - Amazon AI recruitment tool (2018), biased against female candidates.
 - LinkedIn job recommendations, biased toward men.

Several groups also emphasized the importance of matching case studies to participants' industry or role to enhance learning relevance

- Ideal duration of a capacity building program:
 - Flexible, Blended Formats
 - Strong interest in combining shorter online modules with in-person workshops
 - Preference for multi-day formats (2-3 days) with optional follow-up sessions
- Preference for an in person or online format:
 - There was diversity of opinions, often shaped by the sensitivity of the topic:
 - **In-person strongly preferred** by certain groups — due to trust-building, interaction, and engagement.

Emerging Learning Needs

Except for the first point (“Existing courses/training on bias in AI or close-by topics”) expanded in the dedicated paragraph below, the results of the discussion can be summarized in the following table, whereas being the groups mixed in terms of stakeholders' representation, it was not possible to discern the specific input per stakeholder type.

<p>Expected knowledge and information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Understanding AI and its limitations: Providing insights into different AI development stages and AI models, such as machine learning, the logic behind them, and their limitations. ● Get to know existing mitigation tools. ● Introducing the concept of biases and their identification: getting knowledge on bias concepts and its various forms, including their manifestation in AI systems and insight for their identification together with strategies for dealing with them. ● Diversity and equity understanding: improving the capability of diversity and equity principles to promote fairness in AI applications. ● Emerging job opportunities: exploring new job roles created by AI and the opportunities they present. ● AI in HR: exploring AI integration into HR processes and its implications. ● Arguments for AI adoption: providing convincing reasons for staff and owners to adopt AI, emphasizing benefits like improved candidate experience and decision-making processes. ● Diversity in AI: enhancing awareness about the experiences and challenges faced by minority groups in recruitment and beyond. ● Self-awareness: fostering self-awareness of personal biases. ● GDPR awareness: teaching basics about GDPR, personal data and special categories of data.
<p>Expected skills</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Develop critical thinking and dialogue: enhance capabilities of questioning AI system's outputs, fostering trust in individual judgment, and promoting critical dialogue. ● Bias warning signs recognition: develop skills in identifying bias in AI systems and in interpreting data effectively to understand bias. ● Creating safe spaces: support the establishment of environments where biases can be openly discussed and addressed. ● Technical skills: providing technical training to navigate AI systems as well as prompt engineering skills. ● Metrics for equality and fairness: using metrics to measure equality and fairness in AI applications, considering political and contextual choices.
<p>Case studies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Exclusion due to AI filtering: Instances where individuals who may have had less time to craft detailed cover letters or don't perfectly match keywords in job ads are unfairly excluded by AI, despite meeting the requirements. ● Bias in facial recognition for interviews: Cases where AI's use of facial recognition in interviews could introduce bias, such as favoring candidates with better internet connections or depending on lighting conditions. ● Organizational fear of AI in recruitment due to concerns about making poor decisions, and perceptions of bias in tools like LinkedIn. ● Examples of discrimination in AI recruitment: Examples including the Amazon case of AI-driven discrimination in recruitment, studies showing disparities in recommended vacancies on LinkedIn based on gender, and research demonstrating how changing a name on a CV impacts acceptance rates. ● Ali M., Sapienzyński P. et al.'s paper on discrimination through optimization (2019).
<p>Format & length</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Flexible learning formats preferred (combination of in person and online sessions). ● Blended learning approach (using a mix of methods: from e-learning modules, to in-person workshops and mentoring programmes). ● Preference for shorter, more frequent sessions rather long-duration workshops.

Table 2. Emerging learning needs from the international co-creation workshop

Combining inputs both from the interviews and the workshop, the following emerging learning needs were isolated to be adapted and further tailored. These seemed to be crosscutting the different target groups:

- Understanding AI and its limitations: providing insights into different IA development stages such as machine learning, and technical training on how to use AI tools effectively and understand their impact as well as understanding capabilities and constraints of AI technologies. Introducing existing mitigation tools, debiasing methods, accountability strategies and corrective measures (and company providers).
- Introducing the concept of biases and their identification: providing knowledge on bias concepts (philosophical and theoretical assumptions, relationships with prejudices and unconscious bias) and their various forms and dimensions (e.g. gender, race, class, etc.), including their manifestation in AI systems and insight for their identification together with strategies for dealing with them, as well as information on how bias is included in different stages of technological development, from data to output.
- AI in HR: exploring AI integration into HR processes and its implications.
- Diversity in AI: enhancing awareness about the experiences and challenges faced by minority groups in AI-assisted recruitment and beyond.
- Existing regulations and ethics frameworks, including the European AI Act.

3.2.2 Initial benchmarking

Methodology

As planned, SVEN conducted a non-exhaustive, exploratory benchmarking activity with scoping purposes to gain insight into the current offerings of training and courses concerning bias and ethics in AI. The activity mainly consisted in desk research enriched with inputs coming from the above-mentioned interviews and the international co-creation workshop, as well as inputs coming from partners and sister projects. The following keywords served as inclusion criteria: ethics in AI course; bias in AI course; AI in human resources course; gender and AI course; race and artificial intelligence course. The term course was also replaced with capacity building programme/training.

The results of this preliminary mapping were collected on a spreadsheet where the following features/information have been tracked and reported: 1) Title of the course; 2) Source; 3) Organization (organizing/delivering the course); 4) Format (summer school, online course, winter school, training, university course, webinar); 5) Reference person; 6) Target; 7) Topics addressed; 8) Specific grounds of discrimination/bias addressed (if specified); 9) Format (online/in-person/blended); 10) Methods; 11) Duration; 12) Price; 13) Link.

Results

57 courses have been identified and included in the spreadsheet. These are delivered by around 50 different organizations, ranging from universities, private consultancies and online platforms (e.g. LinkedIn Learning).

- **Format:** the great majority of the identified courses were online (45), 6 of those representing university courses.
- **Target Audience:** 30 of the courses target the general public, open to anyone without targeting specific beneficiaries and do not require any skills. 3 courses specifically target women among which 1 also addresses minorities. 3 address students having at least basic knowledge of programming, and 7 address HR professionals. Other courses target other specific professionals such as those working across the financial services sector, healthcare professionals, or companies. Some courses do not clarify their target.

- **Topics addressed:** they cover a broad spectrum of issues, ranging from legal and ethical considerations to workplace applications and skill development, reflecting the multifaceted nature of AI's impact on society, governance and individual lives. The topics covered in the courses can be broadly categorized into the following overarching themes, although this list is not exhaustive:
 - Introduction to AI fundamentals (machine learning and natural language processing) and its applications.
 - Ethics, governance and legal aspects, including regulations such as the GDPR and the AI Act, the understanding of bias and discrimination in AI algorithms, and strategies for mitigation.
 - Social and cultural impacts of AI on gender equality, bias, and inclusion adopting intersectional lenses.
 - Skill development and professional growth including programming skills, data analysis and emotional intelligence for career advancement.
 - AI applications in HR including analysis of ethical implications in workplace contexts and cases regarding discriminatory practices.
- **Focus on discrimination:** 11 courses address gender, 2 race, 1 other socio-economic based biases, 1 women and minorities. A course tackles the following biases: historical bias, representation bias, measurement bias, aggregation bias, evaluation bias, and deployment bias.
- **Learning methods:** methods adopted by the courses are varied. However, online courses are aligned in offering video sessions, readings, quizzes to test the knowledge, and further materials (e.g. slides). In person courses are more likely to introduce group works and workshops, in addition to lectures/presentations. A couple of online courses are structured as MOOCs. In addition, a few courses propose case studies, role plays as well as mentoring activities. Two courses are developed in the form of a bootcamp.
- **Duration:** it can span from several months to a few hours depending on the course. University courses generally have a longer duration, while online ones can be much shorter. In case of online courses, they are also usually “self-paced” suggesting a commitment of a few hours per week.
- **Costs:** Also the cost is varied going from free courses to expensive ones (e.g. around 1.500€/2.000€ for online courses lasting up to few weeks, to about 40.000€ for a residential 4 weeks Master course along one entire years and dissertation assessment).

All in all, the analysis conducted highlighted that there is a lack of training specifically addressing gender, race and intersectional bias in AI solutions and in particular IA applications used within HR and recruitment. Moreover, there is a lack of tailored offer for the specific target groups on the topics at stake that BIAS proposes to cover. Also, in-person and blended formats seem to be less represented suggesting a space for the BIAS offer to cover a gap. Furthermore, the free feature of the BIAS capacity building course could prove to represent an incentive to participation/enrolment.

3.2.3 Pilot testing to refine design

The designed curriculum/script/materials have been pilot-tested in June 2024, in an online format, and subsequently adapted for the first roll-out phase, between February and May 2025.

The piloted 9-hours course “Navigating Bias, Ethics Issues, and Tools in Selection and Recruitment” was designed for HR professionals, held over two days on Zoom, on the 14th and 17th of June 2024. The primary objective of the training was to equip HR professionals with the necessary skills and knowledge to understand and mitigate bias within AI systems, explore the ethical implications of AI adoption, and master the use of AI technologies in recruitment processes. The training also aimed to

foster critical thinking among participants, encouraging them to question AI outputs and to develop a more informed and responsible approach to integrating AI into HR practices. It was attended by 26 participants. An ex-post survey was filled in by 10 participants. In terms of gender, the group was composed of 50% female and 40% male (10% preferred not to say).

Figure 1: Participants' profiles

Based on the ex-post evaluation of the pilot training session, participants' expectations were moderately to highly met: 50% reported being fully satisfied, 33.3% satisfied, and 16.7% partially satisfied.

Figure 2: Overall satisfaction

Regarding content, 60% were fully satisfied with both the relevance to their work and the content itself, while 40% and 30%, respectively, were satisfied and partially satisfied on the content trainings.

Methods of training during the session received more mixed feedback, with 30% fully satisfied, 60% satisfied, 10% partially satisfied, and 10% unsatisfied.

Figure 3: Work- Relevance, Content and Methods

The use of tools, including Zoom and Mural, was positively rated, with 50% fully satisfied and 50% satisfied.

Figure 4: Use of Zoom platform

However, feedback on the schedule and timing was evenly split: 50% of participants found it adequate, while the other 50% considered it not adequate, mainly due to the session being too long. Feedback on trainers was generally positive.

Figure 5: Workshop inputs

Participants were equally split between being fully satisfied and satisfied with the trainers' knowledge. On communication, 40% were fully satisfied, 40% satisfied, and 20% unsatisfied. Use of inclusive language received 60% full satisfaction and 40% satisfaction, while listening and dialogue were rated 60% satisfied, 30% satisfied and 10% partially satisfied.

Figure 6: Specific satisfaction

As this training was a pilot in preparation for the full capacity building programme planned for 2025, the feedback from participants, along with the one from the partners who attended the sessions as observers, informed few key decisions:

- Condense the programme into a 6-hour format and to revise scripts and training materials accordingly.
- Further refine the presentations to increase the rate of met expectations. In particular, the presentation on the policy frameworks needed improvement.
- Further ameliorate the flow of the interactive exercise and the instructions to improve the hands-on component.

3.3 Transversal methodological approach

From the methodological point of view, the design process has been inspired by the training principles applied within the H2020 GE Academy Project, where SVEN was one of the promoting partners and in charge of evaluation. The design of the capacity building course on preventing and mitigating gender and intersectional bias in algorithmic hiring is inspired—albeit with contextual adaptations—by key principles drawn from feminist pedagogies. These pedagogical approaches, rooted in the emancipatory and liberation-oriented educational practices of social movements and influenced by the work of Paulo Freire, emphasize critical engagement, transformation, and inclusivity (Macdonald & Sánchez-Casal, 2002; hooks, 1994). In their feminist reinterpretation, a central role is attributed to critical feminist knowledge, and the explicit focus on exposing and challenging structural and intersectional inequalities, so that the above-mentioned principles are reframed through a gender+ lens ensuring that gender and other intersecting forms of power and exclusion are critically examined.

Three foundational principles have guided the development of the course:

1. Transformative Learning

Learning is not limited to the acquisition of new knowledge but seeks to foster a critical re-evaluation of how knowledge is produced, how reality is interpreted, and how individual experience is understood. This process of reflection and transformation applies equally to both learners and trainers and is referred to as the re-validation of experience. Within the context of AI-driven hiring, transformative learning invites participants to go beyond acquiring technical or regulatory knowledge. It encourages a critical interrogation of how AI systems are designed, deployed, and legitimized—and how these processes often reflect and reinforce existing social inequalities. The capacity building design seeks to foster participants reflective attitude on their own roles, assumptions, and practices in recruitment and technology use, identifying ways in which they may unknowingly contribute to bias, but also exploring opportunities for resistance and structural change. This includes re-reading their personal and professional experiences to uncover how gender+, race, class, age, and other intersecting dimensions shape both access to employment and perceptions of "merit" and "fit."

2. Non-Hierarchical Learning

Feminist pedagogies challenge traditional, top-down educational models. Instead, they promote participatory and egalitarian learning environments, where authority is shared, and trainees are encouraged to actively shape the training process. This includes contributing to the design, content, and materials of the learning experience. In a field often dominated by technical expertise and hierarchical power structures, this principle ensures that the training space is intentionally inclusive and participatory. The courses are designed so to flatten hierarchies not only between trainers and participants but also between disciplines and forms of knowledge—bridging social sciences, HR practices, legal frameworks, and computer science. Attention is given to engaging diverse participants, including those typically underrepresented in conversations around AI and recruitment (e.g., non-technical professionals, junior staff, or people from marginalized communities). Participants are invited to “co-create” the learning process, contribute use cases, and share insights from their own institutional or sectoral contexts.

3. Valuing Experience as a Learning Resource

Knowledge is not confined to formal academic or technical sources. Instead, lived experiences—of both trainees and trainers—are recognized as vital and legitimate sources of insight, contributing to a richer and more grounded learning process. The feminist interpretation of this principle takes on particular importance in the context of emerging technologies, where experiential knowledge is often

undervalued. The course' design foregrounds not only academic and technical sources, but also the lived experiences of individuals affected by AI hiring—such as HR professionals, diversity officers, trade unionists/activists, and AI designers with the aim of fostering the understanding of how bias operates in practice, and how it can be challenged. Moreover, the experiences of participants themselves—especially those working within organizations—are leveraged to reflect on how AI tools are selected, implemented, and evaluated in real-world settings.

In concrete terms, these principles impacted on the design of the script in several ways. On one hand, the adoption of participatory techniques and methodologies (e.g., group works, interactive and participatory tools, etc.) ensured an interactive and hands-on learning approach. All courses aimed at providing evidence based, applicable knowledge on the topics at stake based on State-of-the-Art research, and triggering reflexivity and mutual learning on human-machine interactions in AI-assisted hiring oriented to fairness and prevention of gender, race, and diversity biases.

4 The BIAS courses targeting HR professionals, AI Specialists and trade unions/NGOs

4.1 Final features: target groups, formats and language

The initial **target audiences** identified in the Grant Agreement for the T3.3 “Capacity Building sessions” included: AI researchers, students, practitioners, and HR specialists dealing with AI solutions coming from the academia and private/industry sector. The T2.2 “Learning needs analysis” helped refining and grouping this initial list in 3 different professional profiles:

- AI experts: AI Researcher, Data Engineer, Data Analyst/Scientist, Data scientist, Business Analyst, AI/Machine Learning Engineer, System Architect.
- HR specialists: Recruiting & Selection Manager/Specialists, HR Director/Manager, Training & Development, Manager/Specialists, Personnel Administration Specialist, Employment agencies, Head-hunters, Temporary work agencies.
- Workers Representatives/NGOs: this category covers the need to address workers’ rights when it comes to applying to job positions through AI driven tools, by including beneficiaries such as workers’ representatives and trade union’s officers, as well as representatives of Civil Society Organisations working with minorities and others. During exchanges at the consortium level, it was decided that it would make sense to consider workers representatives as well as beneficiaries for the courses, consistently with the approach used in the co-creation workshops and National Labs in WP2, where TU and CSO were included.

As a result of the design process, a curriculum was defined for the capacity building sessions for each of these three categories.

As far as the **formats** are concerned, both an online and an in-person format have been designed.

- Initially, the online format was planned to adapt to the unpredictable constraints related to the pandemic situation.
- After the end of pandemic restrictions, the online format offered a flexible option, allowing to extend participation beyond the consortium partners’ geographical area.

Based on the Grant Agreement, the proposed duration of the training session was 3 half day sessions for in person events, and 3-hours sessions for online sessions. However, this was adjusted following feedback from participants to the pilot program as well as from consortium partners. Both indicated that the sessions should be shortened, in terms of content included as well as for attracting people with tight schedules. The final adopted format is:

- 2 sessions of three hours or one full day for in-person events.
- 2 sessions of 3 hours each for online sessions.

The workshops are in English, entirely free, and upon registration (limited seat available).

4.2 Key components of the three courses

The three designed courses for AI experts, HR specialists and Workers’ Representatives featured an alternation of input parts/presentations followed by Q&A sessions, with participatory sessions and exercises in smaller groups and/or plenary:

- **Input parts/presentations** aimed at distilling key concepts and knowledge takeaways from the ongoing research work in WP2, 3 and 4, as well as additional resources provided by consortium partners and derived from other courses and sources, mostly (although not exclusively) academic. Among those, SVEN team took part to the FINDHR Project e-learning course, and to the CDCP (Computer, Privacy, Data Protection) conference 2024 in Brussels. Attention was paid to avoiding excessively theoretical

approaches in presentations, and to limit the input parts between 15-20 minutes each. Also, in order to facilitate attention retainment and tailoring to non-academic audiences, visual elements/graphics of the presentations were curated and concrete examples from real-life case studies were integrated in all presentations, with special care for those referring to the more strictly technical components and for HR professionals and CSO/Trade Union, so target beneficiaries with no or limited knowledge of computer sciences/AI could better benefit from the course.

- **Participatory sessions:** in line with adult learning participatory pedagogies, emphasis was placed on the need for fostering group dialogue and relations, and mutual learning among participants. In all courses, inception time was devoted to an introductory ice-breaking session, where trainees could familiarize with each other, followed by carefully designed ad hoc hands-on exercises that aimed at supporting participants in reflecting and envisioning hurdles and opportunities related to using AI in their professional/advocacy activities. 4 different hands-on exercises were designed/applied for this purpose:
 - **The identity wheel exercise** used with both HR professionals and AI specialists. This exercise aims at triggering personal reflection from participants, although applied to the professional/advocacy domains they live in, on direct or indirect experiences of bias/discrimination/privilege, anchoring a complex concept such as intersectional bias in real-life cases. The exercise suggests reflecting on the Identity Wheel ([John Hopkins University. Integrative Learning and Life Design, 2024](#)), which combines intersectional inequalities/identities with different dimensions subject to change over the course of a lifetime (i.e. education, work experience, language, appearance etc). This reflection is proposed at an individual level, suggesting writing on sticky notes individually, and then sharing with the group, only if they feel like it. Addressing private, potentially sensitive topics with other participants/people met for the very first time could be challenging for some, but it is deemed important to operationalize transformative learning principles (see above).
 - **The Value Oriented Design group exercise**, practiced with AI specialists. In this collaborative workshop, participants explore how to embed ethical and social values into the design of AI-driven recruitment tools using the Value Sensitive Design (VSD) approach. Working in small groups, they use [VSD Envisioning Cards](#) to reflect on the values at stake, the direct and indirect stakeholders impacted, and how these values are perceived in relation to the technology. The exercise unfolds in three stages: 1) Stakeholder & Values Mapping - Groups identify stakeholders, desired values, and potential tensions or perceptions related to AI in hiring. 2) The Design Pipeline - Participants examine each phase of the AI development process, brainstorming how values can be translated into concrete design choices. 3) Prototyping - Groups sketch out a conceptual prototype, integrating ethical considerations into technical elements such as data sources, algorithms, evaluation methods, and post-deployment support. Sample tools and applications are available for inspiration.
 - **The ETUI AI Board Game** for Trade Unions/NGOs representatives. The [AI Board Game](#) is an engaging, educational tool created by the European Trade Union Institute (ETUI) to examine the complex ways in which AI is transforming the world of work. Aimed at workers' representatives, trade union trainers, members of European Works Councils, digitalisation officers, and social partners, the game is designed to build awareness and spark meaningful dialogue about the opportunities and challenges AI presents in different workplace contexts. By integrating foresight principles, horizon-scanning, and

immersive role-play, the ETUI AI Board Game fosters informed discussions and negotiations regarding the implementation and impact of AI technologies in their respective sectors. ([Ponce del Castillo, ETUI, 2023](#)).

- **Challenging AI. The Hiring BlackBox group exercise**, proposed to HR professionals. This exercise is an adapted version of the international co-creation session held in Venice in December 2023 within T2.3 (see D.2.4⁴). It integrates a real human-machine interaction dynamic in the training setting promising to create a powerful thought-provoking moment for participants. In this exercise, they engage in a simulated hiring process to critically examine how candidate evaluations are made and how algorithmic systems influence decision-making. The activity begins with a group reading and analysis of a fictitious job description, followed by a prioritization of key requirements. Each participant reviews one or more (fictitious) candidate profiles and compares them against the identified criteria. After individual assessments, the group collectively ranks the candidates and discusses their reasoning. The second part introduces the “[Hiring Black Box](#)”—a simplified AI tool connected to GPT4 that processes the same candidates’ data based on a predefined prompt. Participants explore how the system generates its output and compare the AI-generated ranking with their own, sparking discussion on transparency, bias, and the implications of algorithmic decision-making in recruitment.

The next paragraph details the transversal objectives and common content to the designed three curricula (AI experts, HR specialists and Workers Representatives/NGOs), as well as common participative methodology.

Later, the following paragraphs present specific objectives and related content for each of the three curricula (AI experts, HR specialists, and Workers Representatives/NGOs), as well hands-on exercises for the specific target audiences.

4.3 Learning objectives and content-related sessions transversal to all target groups

The transversal learning objectives identified for the training courses targeting all 3 groups are:

- Understand and mitigate gender and diversity bias with an intersectional perspective.
- Navigate the ethical considerations of AI.
- Develop a critical thinking approach to human-machine interaction in the use of AI applied to workplace domains.
- Explore the complex role of AI within HRM, focusing on its potentials and challenges in terms of ethics and fairness, in a dynamic setting based on participatory and inclusive adult learning methods.
- Navigate legal and ethical frameworks: understand frameworks such as the AI Act, GDPR, and anti-discrimination laws, and discuss their implications for ethical AI development and deployment.
- Access a peer-to-peer open space for learning, dialogue, and collaboration.

In all three curricula, there are two transversal input sessions, with some minor adaptations to better cater the different target groups:

- The presentation on framing the meaning and key definitions of bias and its socio/psychological implications to convey the message of the interlocking of human and algorithmic bias.

⁴ D2.4, Final report on co-creation methodologies and findings

- The policy framework presentation, describing the AI Act frame and how it applies/needs to be integrated with GDPR and anti-discrimination legislation.

4.4 The course for HR specialists: specificities

Specific learning objectives

- AI models: learn the logic and mechanics behind various AI models, their capabilities, and limitations in HR.
- AI in recruitment: understand challenges and opportunities of AI tools used in recruitment and assess their impact on candidate experience and decision-making.

Dedicated content sessions

- Elements of AI:
 - Basics of AI: definitions strong/weak AI, machine learning and its applications.
 - Supervised/unsupervised learning, and supervised learning for hiring.
 - NLP (natural language processing) and word embedding.
 - Social stereotypes in word embedding; Word Embedding Association Test (WEAT).
 - Ethical and social implications of AI in terms of bias: source of algorithmic discriminations; types of biases in AI, automation bias; AI hallucinations; algorithmic de-biasing/auditing.
 - The policy framework: the existing framework, AI Act (including a small quiz); GDPR; Anti-discrimination law; use of sensitive data and the “Schufa” case⁵.
 - AI in recruitment: existing tools and systems and case studies of bias in recruitment using AI: Algorithmic hiring; hiring tools and systems using AI and related risks; case Studies of bias in recruitment due to AI systems: challenges for HR and companies; Information Access Systems; Decoy effect in hiring; Algorithmic decision making to reduce or detect discriminations; concept of fairness in recruitment.

Hands-on exercises

- Self-reflection exercises: the tool of the “Identity wheel” offers an opportunity for participants to examine personal biases and privileges. Participants reflect individually on the following guiding questions, adapted to the target audience:
 - How personal identity features such as race, age, gender, gender identity, etc. (see internal part of the wheel) have shaped my work experience and my (previous or current) organizational role?
 - How those features, as well as the other ones represented on the outside part of the wheel, and intersections of those, have contributed to put me in a privileged or disadvantaged position in my work experience and organizational role?
 - How might certain biases I hold have shaped my “work experience” and “organizational role”?
 - For in presence format, participants add sticky notes with their reflections on a poster on a wall, visible to all participants to stimulate shared reflection.
- Challenging AI - a group exercise (see above). Participants work in groups of 4-5 people each and the exercise is divided in 4 activities, following the instructions summarized above (and available in the slide-set and materials of the course). After simulating a full human-centred ranking and having consulted the [Hiring Black Box](#) based on the

⁵ Judgment - 07/12/2023 - SCHUFA Holding (Scoring) Case C-634/21.

received results, participants discuss on the ranking and explanations, answering 3 questions:

- Do you agree with the final ranking? Why?
- Are there any considerations and/or candidates' features that the machine took into consideration and the group did not? And vice versa? Which ones?
- Are the explanations sufficient for decision-support?
- In Plenary: each group represented by a spokesperson brings feedback on the replies on the key 3 questions.

4.5 The course for IA experts: specificities

Specific learning objectives

- Apply Value Sensitive Design (VSD): use VSD principles to evaluate the socio-technical impact of AI, with a focus on fairness and ethics in design choices.
- Design and evaluate fair AI models: collaborate to develop and test algorithms using fairness metrics and Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) principles, critically evaluating their performance in hiring and recruitment.

Dedicated content sessions

- Socio-technical implications of AI and fairness approaches: introduction to VSD; go through the pipeline of designing a candidate ranking tool; introducing AI concepts as needed and using VSD to point out sociotechnical consequences of design choices.
- The policy framework: the existing framework: AI Act, GDPR, Anti-discrimination law, ALTAI principles; direct/indirect discrimination; open discussion on the implications of policies in AI design.
- Operationalizing VSD and fairness approaches: fairness approaches reviewed with critical lenses and fairness metrics; Case-Based Reasoning (CBR) as an alternative AI model built with specific values (e.g., transparency, procedural fairness).

Participatory methodology: hands-on exercises

- Self-reflection exercises: "Identity wheel". It offers an opportunity for participants to examine personal biases and privileges. They reflect individually on the following guiding questions, adapted to computer scientists:
 - How your identities had an influence in your study/professional choices in Computer Sciences and/or Engineering?
 - How do your identities influence your work as a Computer Scientist/Engineer?
 - For in presence format, participant add sticky notes with their reflection on a poster on a wall, visible to all participants to stimulate shared reflection.

4.6 The course for workers' representatives/NGOs: specificities

Specific learning objectives

- Key AI concepts and workplace applications: Define core AI concepts and identify common workplace applications, emphasizing their impact on workers and organizations.
- AI risks in recruitment: explore case studies to identify risks in AI-driven recruitment, including algorithmic bias and the decoy effect, and review methods like auditing and de-biasing for fair hiring practices.

Dedicated content sessions

- AI and its ethical and social implication: source of algorithmic discriminations; human biases from the psychological and sociological perspective; confirmation bias and systemic bias; types of biases in AI, automation bias, AI hallucinations; algorithmic de-biasing/auditing.
- AI in recruitment: bias and case studies: algorithmic hiring and related risks; case Studies of bias in recruitment due to AI systems: challenges for applicants; bias in recruitment and decoy effect; algorithmic decision making to reduce or detect discriminations; concept of fairness in recruitment.
- The policy framework: the AI Act; Legal case on automated decision making; the role of Workers Representatives and NGOs: some case studies; AI and collective bargaining: some examples; how AI can be leveraged to protect workers' rights.

Hands-on exercises

As mentioned above the hands-on part of the course for trade unionists and NGOs representatives draws on the AI game developed by ETUI, the European Trade Union Institute, that provided the needed material (board games, games' cards and instructions) and briefed the SVEN team on how to use the game in practice. For the AI board game, some material has been adapted to the BIAS training, the cards including challenges related to AI in recruitment, adding specific cases derived from the ongoing ethnographic research in WP4, that will be integrated in the official version of the game and contribute to enrich it.

- **AI & the Workplace: a group exercise.** The AI game allows participants to familiarize with definitions related to AI technologies and brainstorm about their possible uses in the workplace. The game is organised in the following steps:
 - Individually: participants individually go through the different definitions provided and identify the ones that they do not know.
 - In Group: participants discuss about the unknown technologies considering technologies with immediate, mid-term, long-term impact.
 - For each immediate, mid-term, long term impact scenarios, participants collectively pick up one technology and discuss its potential benefits and risks.
 - Based on previous discussions, participants summarize 3 main challenges and opportunities linked to AI in the workspace.
 - In Plenary: each group represented by a spokesperson brings feedback on the 3 main challenges and opportunities identified for AI in the workspace.
- **AI Board game: a group exercise.** Role play and scenarios are used to make participants brainstorm and discuss different issues and challenges related to the use of AI. The aim of the game is to acquire as many AI technologies as possible while solving the many challenges encountered. The game is organised in the following steps:
 - Each group receives a board game.
 - Each participant chooses a role: AI system developer, entrepreneurs/start-ups/Education-Technology companies, government, employer, workers, unions, parents, consumer associations, NGOs for vulnerable groups, environmental NGOs, human rights activists, civil society organizations.
 - Moves forwards on the board game, using pawns and dices.
 - Reflects individually on technology (smart camera, virtual classrooms, chat bots, virtual teachers, metaverse etc.) and its impact on issues related to it (stress, inequality, power imbalance etc.), when picking up technology/issues cards.
 - Collectively solves challenges' issues when picking up a challenge card, related to AI and workspace, each participant reflecting the chosen role.
 - Two levels of challenges:

- Individual, the person who collects the most coins at the table, wins.
- Collective, the group who solves collectively more challenges, wins.
- Plenary discussion: each group represented by a spokesperson brings feedback on the number of challenges solved and a group winner is identified.

5 Training team

Each session is covered by two trainers, ensuring the complex set of skills needed to deliver the courses including the bias, ethics and inclusiveness part of the training, and the tech component.

5.1 Coordination of the capacity building design process & “Train the trainers” session

Maria Sangiuliano: she holds a Ph.D. in Cognitive and Learning Studies and has extensive expertise in capacity building, learning design, and participatory methodologies. Her work is dedicated to creating sustainable and inclusive innovation processes through diversity-sensitive co-design and implementation. Research Director at SVEN, specializing in gender equality within innovation ecosystems, she has 20 years of experience in designing and implementing EU-funded interventions focusing on mainstreaming gender in innovation policies, employment, and education, emphasizing intersectionality and multicultural integration.

5.2 Field experts in AI & Fairness/Ethics

With a specific background in AI, the field experts have already developed expertise in applying gender and diversity, socially oriented approaches to computer sciences. They have been identified within the project’s consortium partners as the most suitable for delivering the capacity building training (or similar sentence showing they are not strangers) They are responsible for:

- Preparing for and delivering engaging training sessions using the provided curriculum, training scripts slide sets, and templates/tools.
- Provide feedback and post-training insights in the form of a short report to support program evaluation.

Alexandre Puttick: postdoctoral Researcher at Berner Fachhochschule in Research in applied machine learning in mental health and the labour market. He is a Pure Mathematics PhD, with more than 4 years of academic experience. His skills relate to: Mathematical logic and reasoning, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Statistics and Mathematical Modelling.

Simona Lo Giudice: researcher at Torino University and Expert/Trainer at Smart Venice. She is an Engineer and Data Scientist with background in Natural Language Processing, with more than 4 years of professional experience. She is committed in advancing research and knowledge in the interdisciplinary field of AI and Ethics.

5.3 Facilitators

With diverse backgrounds spanning from political sciences to international relations and development, and gender equality policies, the facilitators have complemented their profiles with a dedicated Train the Trainers programme at SVEN including an e-learning course, and face to face sessions. The three facilitators support the professional trainers in the delivery of the capacity building program, as well as the consortium partners in handling the courses’ logistics.

Maria Giovanna Zamburlini is project manager at SVEN, with an EU studies master and over a decade of experience in EU project development and management, mostly on topics related to inclusive urban development.

Arianna Montera is Gender and Equality Expert at SVEN. She has a MA background in Politics, Philosophy and Public Affairs and earned a specialization course on Gender & Diversity Policies. Arianna has worked in supporting Research Organizations in designing and implementing Gender Equality Plans.

Rogério Moreira Junior is Administrative and Communications Officer & Program Management Assistant, bringing a strong interdisciplinary background in European policies, global communication, and socio-political analysis.

6 Evaluation process and tools

The main purpose of the evaluation is to support the redesign of the training (M31–35: May - September 2025) before the second roll-out planned in M36–38 (October - December 2025), as well as to feed the design and development of the EU-level e-learning course, under T5.4 “E-learning course”. The evaluation methodology developed and the results of the evaluation itself will be collected and included in an overall report to be finalized in M46, at the end of the project.

The evaluation of the training is based on the Donabedian framework used within the GE Academy Horizon 2020 Project (Donabedian, 1966), which organizes assessment into three categories:

1. Structure (logistics, tools, platforms, and trainer quality)
2. Process (communication, methodologies, and trainer-participant interaction)
3. Outcome (participant satisfaction, increased knowledge, skills, and gender balance).

The evaluation primarily uses qualitative methods, including analysis of training materials, on-site observation by BIAS partners and the SVEN team, and consortium-level workshops. In contrast, quantitative methods are used to collect participant feedback via surveys, while trainers conduct peer evaluations using a dedicated observation grid.

The evaluation process is organized in several steps, in the preparation phase, during the training and ex post.

Preparation phase and upon registration

- **Ex-ante survey:** sent to registered participants to better define the profiles of people in the room and their expectations. The ex-ante survey is collected through a Google Form hosted by SVEN, including several questions related to:
 - Personal information (email, name, gender, job title, special needs required to participate in the session).
 - Level of experience with AI and recruitment and previous experience on one or more of the topics of the course.
 - Learning expectations of the training (namely: understand bias in AI and HR; Evaluate AI’s potential and limitations; How to Balance AI insights with human judgment; Develop strategies for fair and inclusive hiring).
 - GDPR compliant message, asking agreement on sharing contact emails with other participants.

During training

During the training, observations are collected by trainers at the event.

- **Peer-Evaluation between the trainers:** the trainers exchange impressions during the training, collecting first impression from partners organization co-hosting and informal impressions from participants.

Ex -post evaluation

- **Peer-Evaluation between the trainers:** the trainers involved fill-in for each session the “Template for Checklist for self-evaluation”, providing feedback on challenging issues raised during the training, related to the training’s structure, process and outcome.
- **Ex post survey:** the training participants are invited to fill in **an anonymous** ex-post questionnaire with several questions through a Google Form hosted by SVEN. The questions look for the following elements:
 - Level of satisfaction in terms of learning expectation.

- Level of appreciation concerning the content and organisation of the session (relevance for the person's work/advocacy activities, sessions' content and interactivity, room logistics and catering).
- Level of appreciation for trainers (trainers' knowledge on the topic; their communication capacities, their use of gender sensitive language).
- Level of appreciation for methods and approaches (interactivity and participation; knowledge and tools suitable to be put in practice; opportunities to reflect on your own beliefs/behaviours; quality and accessibility of documentation; equipment and technical support; timing/breaks).

7 First roll-out: schedule, participants, preliminary considerations

The design of the capacity building program has been tested in the initial pilot test (M20-21) in June 2024 and adapted for the first roll-out phases (M28–30), taking place between February and beginning of May 2025. Here below the list of capacity building sessions.

Pilot Test

A first pilot session took place online on Friday, 14th and Monday 17th June 2024 designed as an immersive training specifically for HR professionals, hosted by SVEN (see chapter 2).

Roll -Out Session

The first roll out session takes place between February and beginning of May among the 9 BIAS partners.

N	Host	Date	Place	Target	Registrants	Participants	Communication Articles on BIAS website
1	SVEN	14-17/06 2024 (Pilot)	Online	HR specialists	45	26	Link
2	SVEN	20-21/02 2025	Riccione	Workers Representatives	31	24	Link
3	ULEI	14/03/2025	Leiden	HR specialists	29	25	Link
4	LOBA	17/03/2025	Porto	HR specialists	11	10	Link
5	HI	25/03 & 01/04/ 2025	Online	HR specialists	60	27	Link
6	NTNU	27/03/2025	Trondheim	AI experts	32	24	Link
7	DIGI	9-10 April 2025	Tallin	AI experts	36	12	Link
8	CHX	15 April 2025	Online	AI experts	43	0, cancelled	
9	BFH	28 April 2025	Online	HR specialists	37	10	Link
10	FARPLAS	9 May 2025	Istanbul	HR specialists	27 ⁶		

Table 3. Pilot and first roll-out schedule and overview

Preliminary considerations

At this stage, only preliminary considerations are available on the capacity building sessions' outcome and their related emerged challenges, that will be the subject of forthcoming discussion at the WP5 and consortium coordination levels.

The collected exit surveys so far show a high level of overall satisfaction from respondents. Impression from fields experts and hosting partners are based on observations during the sessions

⁶ Number available on 28/04/2025.

and first -hands participants' feedback, and from those a shared appreciation on the sessions 'content/inputs, as well as their participatory approaches is emerging. Suggestions for improvement relate mainly to adjustment to content/inputs (e.g.: on the session dedicated to policy framework and the Artificial Intelligence Act -AIA and its bibliography, or the introductory session on Sociological and Psychological underpinnings of BIAS that could be made more specific to HR and interactive than the current version).

In terms of challenges, the second roll-out sessions design should consider:

- Participants dropping off between registrations and participation phase, particularly for online courses (see Table 3, below).
- Limited recruitment and engagement for HR profiles, as visible from the restrained number of participants for sessions in Porto (LOBA) and session for Iceland (HI).
- In general, difficulty in reaching out to the initially expected target of 35 participants per session, in spite of the substantial engagement and dissemination efforts.
- Difficult to keep separate participants profiles in sessions; some hosting partners, such as DIGI and CHX, advertised the course to different profiles, to increase potential participants' reach-out. While this has a positive effect on the recruitment of participants, it might impact the effectiveness of the delivery and satisfaction from participants who receive a training that was designed and tailored to target specific categories of stakeholders.

8 Conclusive remarks in view of the redesign and second roll-out

The full program of the first roll-out capacity building ends with the last planned workshop in Istanbul, on 9th of May.

The collected materials, including the evaluation tools, are fundamental aspects in the evaluation process for improvements. SVEN will look with attention at the following elements:

- Final number of attendees, both for online and in presence format.
- Feedback from participants via the anonymous ex-post survey.
- Feedback from trainers hosting the capacity buildings.
- Feedback from co-hosting partners organisations.

The main purpose of D5.1 is to both detail and unpack the courses design process and the features of the programme in its first iteration. Furthermore, the Deliverable will support the redesign of the training (M31–35: May -September 2025), in view of the second edition of the programme (second roll-out) to be implemented between M36–38 (October, and December 2025).

As indicated in the section “Evaluation Tools”, the evaluation methodology developed and the results of the evaluation itself will be collected and included in an overall report to be finalized as part of D5.3 “Capacity building evaluation methodology and final report” due in M46 (August 2026).

9 Annexes

9.1 Programmes and scripts of capacity building sessions

9.1.1 Programme and script for AI experts

1st session (3 hours)

Time	Programme	Specific contents	Notes
25 minutes	Welcoming and introduction	Introduction to the training, agenda and ice breaking exercise	<p>An ice-breaking exercise can be proposed to help participants getting to know each other.</p> <p>In <u>person training</u>: Participants are asked to stand up and move randomly around the room for 1 minute. Then the trainer rings a bell and they are asked to stop and join other participants in order to create groups of 5 people each. Groups have 5 minutes to do a short round of introduction. Each participant introduces him/herself giving by saying: name, surname, organization they work in, motivation for joining the training and how they feel (with a word).</p> <p>After 5 minutes, the trainer rings a bell and ask participants to walk again randomly for another minute and the ringing the bell again the trainer gives the same instructions as before.</p> <p>If time allows it can be done a third time.</p> <p><u>Online training</u>: an online board (like Padlet) can be used to ask participants to introduce themselves by saying: their name, surname, organization they work in, motivation for joining the training, and how they feel (with a word). This way, all participants can have a look at other presentations.</p> <p>When introducing the training anticipate that the core for the success of the training is sharing and participating and invite participants any time they want to intervene to introduce themselves.</p>

Time	Programme	Specific contents	Notes
40 min	<p>What is a bias? Psychological & sociological underpinnings and self-reflection exercise (slides 25-49)</p>	<p>Presentation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Introducing origins and concepts of bias from psychological and sociological points of view. 2) Distinction of “stereotypes”, “prejudices” and “discrimination”. 3) Concept of systems of oppression/intersectionality. 4) Concept of “unconscious bias”, confirmation bias. Overlap between statistical and human biases (20 min) 5) Self-reflection exercise (10 min) 6) Sharing session - 10 min 	<p>The self-reflection exercise makes use of the “Identity wheel” asking participants to reflect on experienced inequalities/privileges in their working lives. We plan to formulate the guiding questions provided in the link to adapt them to computer scientists, i.e. how your identities had an influence in your study/professional choices in Computer Sciences and/or Engineering? How do your identities influence your work as a Computer Scientists/Engineer?</p> <p>In case of in-person training it is possible to make participants brainstorm around the 3 questions individually and then add notes on sticky notes to be attached on a poster on a wall. The poster can be divided into 3 parts each part representing one question.</p>
10 min	break		
1 hour	Socio-technical implications of AI and fairness approaches	<p>Presentation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Source of algorithmic discriminations, types of biases in AI, automation bias, AI hallucinations, algorithmic hiring; hiring tools and systems using AI and related risks; Case Studies of bias in recruitment due to AI systems 2) Intro to Value Sensitive Design (VSD) 3) Go through the pipeline of designing a candidate ranking 	<p>33 slides (not including transition slides)</p> <p>*45 minutes is a long presentation that in case of a training course we usually split in 2 allocating sometime in the middle to interactive exercises/Q&A</p>

Time	Programme	Specific contents	Notes
		<p>tool, introducing AI concepts as needed and using VSD to point out sociotechnical consequences of design choices.</p> <p>Q&A 15 min</p>	
40 min	1. The policy framework	<p>Presentation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The existing framework: AI Act, GDPR, Anti-discrimination law, ALTAI principles. 2) Direct/indirect discrimination. 3) Open discussion: which are the implications of policies in AI design? <p>Q&A (10 min)</p>	
5 min	1. Wrap-up and conclusions		

2nd session (3 hours)

Time	Programme	Specific contents	Notes
5 min	Welcoming and agenda of the day	Introduction to the agenda of the day	
30 min	Operationalizing VSD and fairness approaches	<p>Presentation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Fairness approaches reviewed with critical lenses and fairness metrics 	

Time	Programme	Specific contents	Notes
		2) CBR as an alternative AI model built with specific values (e.g., transparency, procedural fairness) Q&A (5 min)	
35	The Value Oriented Design Challenge: design your prototype -first part	First part of the exercise: preliminary brainstorming using VSD cards	<p>Participants will work in groups of 4-5 people each.</p> <p>The goal of the preliminary brainstorming is to explore how to embed values into the design of AI tools in HR by using the Envisioning Cards as a structured approach to guide reflection and group discussion. Participants will think about the values involved in AI design, the stakeholders who will be impacted by the technology, and how those values can be integrated effectively into AI systems.</p> <p>Envisioning cards are available here https://vsdesign.org/toolkits/envisioningcards/</p> <p>It is suggested to print them in case of in-person training or embed them in collaborative tools like Mural or Miro.</p> <p>Instructions on how to guide the brainstorming activity are provided in the slide set.</p>
10 min	Break		
1 hour	The Value Oriented Design Challenge: design your prototype - second part	Second part of the exercise: groups will have to design a prototype ranking tool, or use the existing Black Box Tool, enriched with more synthetic data, as a basis	<p>Participants in the same groups design an AI based ranking tool. They will first select the most relevant values from the ALTAI list and then proceed with the design.</p> <p>Instructions and guiding questions provided in the slide set</p>
30 min	Plenary session		
10 min	Wrap up, ex post questionnaire and conclusions		

9.1.2 Programme and script for HR specialists

1st session (3 hours)

Duration	Programme	Specific content	Notes
25 minutes	Welcoming and introduction	Introduction to the training, agenda and ice breaking exercise	<p>An ice-breaking exercise can be proposed to help participants getting to know each other.</p> <p><u>In person training:</u> Participants are asked to stand up and move randomly around the room for 1 minute. Then the trainer rings a bell and they are asked to stop and join other participants in order to create groups of 5 people each. Groups have 5 minutes to do a short round of introduction. Each participant introduces him/herself giving by saying: name, surname, organization they work in, motivation for joining the training and how they feel (with a word).</p> <p>After 5 minutes, the trainer rings a bell and ask participants to walk again randomly for another minute and the ringing the bell again the trainer gives the same instructions as before.</p> <p>If time allows it can be done a third time.</p> <p><u>Online training:</u> an online board (like Padlet) can be used to ask participants introducing themselves by saying: name, surname, organization they work in, motivation for joining the training and how they feel (with a word). This way all participants can have a look to other presentations.</p> <p>House Keeping Rules: when introducing the training anticipate that core for the success of the training is sharing and participating and invite participants any time they want to intervene to firstly introduce themselves.</p>
40 min	What is a bias? Psychological & sociological underpinnings and self-reflection exercise	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Presentation 2) Introducing origins and concepts of bias from psychological and sociological points of view. 	<p>The self-reflection exercise makes use of the Diversity Wheel The diversity wheel from Johns Hopkins University & Medicine’s Diversity Leadership Council. Where the center of the wheel represents individual personal dimensions that are usually most permanent or visible. The outside of the wheel represents dimensions that are mostly acquired and change over the course of a lifetime. Participants are asked to focus on</p>

Duration	Programme	Specific content	Notes
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3) Distinction of “stereotypes”, “prejudices” and “discrimination”. 4) Concept of systems of oppression/intersectionality. 5) Concept of “unconscious bias”, confirmation bias 6) Unlearning unconscious bias (15 min) 7) Self-reflection exercise (5 min) . Sharing session - 20 min (including questions on the presentation) 	<p>“work experience” and “organizational role” as external dimensions and reflect on the following points in Mural and add their reflections using sticky notes.</p> <p>1- How personal identity features such as race, age, gender, gender identity, etc. (see internal part of the wheel) have shaped my work experience and my (previous or current) organizational role and contributed to put me in a privileged or disadvantaged position in my work experience and organizational role?</p> <p>2- Did any of those privilege or disadvantage experiences have (or could have had) anything to do with use of technologies in the working environment?</p> <p>In case of in-person training it is possible to make participants reflect around the 3 questions individually and then add notes on sticky notes and attach them on a poster on a wall. The poster can be divided into 3 parts each part representing one question.</p>
40 min	Elements of AI	<p>Presentation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Basics of AI: definitions, strong/weak AI, machine learning and its applications 2) Supervised/unsupervised learning, and supervised learning for hiring 3) NLP (natural language processing) and word embedding 4) social stereotypes in word embedding 5) WEAT. <p>Q&A 15 min</p>	

Duration	Programme	Specific content	Notes
10 min	break		
30 min	Ethical and social implications of AI in terms of bias	Presentation: 1) Source of algorithmic discriminations, 2) types of biases in AI, 3) automation bias, 4) AI hallucinations, 5) algorithmic de-biasing/auditing. Q&A 10 min	
30 min	The policy framework	Presentations: 1) The existing framework: AI Act (including a small quiz), GDPR, Anti-discrimination law. 2) Use of sensitive data and the "Schufa" case Q&A (10 min)	The quiz is aimed to test the awareness of the different level of risks included in the AI Act.

2nd session (3 hours)

Duration	Programme	Specific content	Notes
1 hour	AI in recruitment: existing tools and systems and case studies of bias in recruitment using AI.	Presentation: 1) Algorithmic hiring 2) Hiring tools and systems using AI and related risks 3) Case Studies of bias in recruitment due to AI	It includes also a short individual exercise, right after the Information Access Systems block (10 minutes), in which participants are asked to search for a gender-neutral job title in Google, Bing or other search engines, such as successful CEO, competent nurse and experienced truck driver. They have then to select an image from the first 15 results and paste it in a Padlet. A short discussion follows.

Duration	Programme	Specific content	Notes
		<p>systems: challenges for HR and companies.</p> <p>4) Information Access Systems (+ 10 minutes exercise)</p> <p>5) Decoy effect in hiring</p> <p>6) Algorithmic decision making to reduce or detect discriminations</p> <p>7) Concept of fairness in recruitment (50 min)</p> <p>Q&A (10 min)</p>	
15 min	Break		
1 hour	Challenging AI - A group exercise	<p>Group exercise using a candidate ranker created by the project using ChatGPT.</p> <p>Goals of the exercise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - have a first-hand experience of interaction with an AI-based technology for HR selection - explore strengths and weaknesses of the technology - develop critical thinking when interacting with AI 	<p>Participants are divided in groups of 4 people each or more. Each of them having a profile of a candidate (with CV and cover letter), 1 job offer and have to decide which candidate better fits the position. Beforehand they discuss it without the use of the technology focusing on the most important features given the role.</p> <p>After, they consult the technology and discuss about the results. (note that they don't need to fill the final questionnaire in the Black Box, they can use the guiding questions there guidelines for discussion without feeling pressured to complete all of the questions). Break out rooms will be used in case of online training. In case of in-person training, each group will need to have at least one computer to run the application.</p> <p>https://blackbox.biasproject.eu/</p>

Duration	Programme	Specific content	Notes
		- challenge participants biases and understand how they interfere and influence the selection procedure	
30 min	Plenary session		
15 min	Wrap up, ex post questionnaire and conclusions		Call to register to the National Lab! include dedicated Quick Response (QR) code.

9.1.3 Programme and script for Workers' Representatives/NGOs

1st session (3 hours)

Time	Programme	Specific content	Notes
25 minutes	Welcoming and introduction	Introduction to the training, agenda and ice breaking exercise	<p>An ice-breaking exercise can be proposed to help participants getting to know each other.</p> <p><u>In person training:</u> Participants are asked to stand up and move randomly around the room for 1 minute. Then the trainer rings a bell, and they are asked to stop and join other participants to create groups of 5 people each. Groups have 5 minutes to do a short round of introduction. Each participant introduces him/herself giving by saying: name, surname, organization they work in, motivation for joining the training and how they feel (with a word).</p>

Time	Programme	Specific content	Notes
			<p>After 5 minutes, the trainer rings a bell and ask participants to walk again randomly for another minute and the ringing the bell again the trainer gives the same instructions as before.</p> <p>If time allows it can be done a third time.</p> <p><u>Online training:</u> an online board (like Padlet) can be used to ask participants introducing themselves by saying: name, surname, organization they work in, motivation for joining the training and how they feel (with a word). This way all participants can have a look to other presentations.</p> <p>When introducing the training anticipate that core for the success of the training is sharing and participating and invite participants when they want to intervene to firstly introduce themselves.</p>
90 min	AI & The Workplace: a group exercise	<p>Group exercise to allow participants familiarize with definitions related to AI technologies and brainstorm about their possible usages in the workplace (60 min).</p> <p>Plenary session (30 min)</p>	<p>The exercise has been elaborated by ETUI. It consists of a canvas structured in 4 different tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - participants individually go through the different definitions provided and identify the ones that do not know. Then in group participants discuss about the unknown technologies (15 min) - the group discusses the possible applications of the AI technologies. In particular, the group receives a set of cards and chooses 3-4 cards per each timeframe (today, very near future, distant future) and discuss about such technologies (20 min). - The group picks up a technology per each timeframe and discusses about their benefits and risks (15 min). - As final task the group formulates 3 key challenges and 3 key opportunities for AI in the workplace (10 min). <p>Ideally the exercise is played in person.</p>

Time	Programme	Specific content	Notes
15 min	break		
40 min	AI and its ethical and social implication	Presentation 1) Source of algorithmic discriminations, 2) human biases from the psychological and sociological perspective, 3) confirmation bias and systemic bias, 4) types of biases in AI, automation bias, AI hallucinations, 5) algorithmic de-biasing/auditing. Q&A 10 min	
5 min	Wrap-up and conclusions		

Time	Programme	Specific contents	Notes
35 min	AI in recruitment: bias and case studies	Presentation: 1) Algorithmic hiring and related risks 2) Case Studies of bias in recruitment due to AI systems: challenges for applicants 3) Bias in recruitment and decoy effect 4) Algorithmic decision making to reduce or detect discriminations 5) Concept of fairness in recruitment (20 min) Q&A (10 min)	
30 min	The policy framework	Presentation: 1) The AI Act 2) Legal case on automated decision making 3) The role of TUs and NGOs: some case studies. 4) AI and collective bargaining: some examples 5) How AI can be leveraged to protect workers' rights Q&A (10 min)	

Time	Programme	Specific contents	Notes
15 min	break		
1 hour	AI Board game	Group exercise that uses role play and scenarios to make participants brainstorm and discuss different issues and challenges related to the use of AI. The aim of the game is to acquire as many AI technologies as possible while solving the many challenges encountered.	<p>4-8 players.</p> <p>Each player is assigned a role in society, e.g. AI system developer, entrepreneur, government, worker, trade union, NGO etc.</p> <p>Participants throw a dice to move their figures across the board, buying or gaining AI technology on the way. They land on “AI issues” and “AI challenges”. When landing on “AI issues” the participants brainstorm on how to solve the issue using the technology, while when landing on “AI challenges” the whole group discusses the challenge/scenario taking the standpoint or interest of the role that they are representing, and aiming to find a solution accommodating every role and taking account of all implications, e.g., legal, environmental, privacy, human rights, etc.</p> <p>The participant collecting more coins wins.</p> <p>Ideally the exercise is played in person.</p>
30 min	Plenary session		
10 min	Wrap up, ex post questionnaire and conclusions		

9.2 Evaluation Tools

9.2.1 Ex ante survey

Template available on Google Form: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdCR5r-2NRgus0wQ-KMJr-Gb6Qs7UYqW1nAvT-jU_81PquURQ/viewform?usp=dialog

Exploratory Survey on BIAS training

mariagiovanna.zamburlini@smartvenice.org [Cambia account](#)

* Indica una domanda obbligatoria

Email *

Il tuo indirizzo email

Your full name *

La tua risposta

Your job title

La tua risposta

Gender

- Female
- Male
- Non Binary
- Srefer not to say
- Altro:

How would you define your experience and knowledge of AI applied to HR/Recruitment? *

- I have no experience/knowledge
- Basic
- Intermediate
- Advanced

Did you already attended trainings on one or more of the topics of this course? *

- Yes
- No

If you answered yes, which specific topics were addressed within the training?

La tua risposta

Which topics would you like to learn about during the training? *

	Very much interested	Interested	Somehow/moderately interested	Not interested
Understand bias in AI and HR	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Evaluate AI's potential and limitations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
How to Balance AI insights with human judgment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Develop strategies for fair and inclusive hiring	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Any other reflections on your expectations towards the training course? *

La tua risposta

Please, do kindly share any special needs that we need to take into account to facilitate your participation

La tua risposta

Do you accept that your contacts will be shared with other participants of the training sessions? *

Yes

No

Avanti

Cancella modulo

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Google Moduli

9.2.2 Ex post survey template

Template available on Google Form:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeCewtpXbBAeDzimJYdlhhvE_C9hoC-hW2NIDP-Mo2sc1yEA/viewform?usp=sf_link

"Webinar Title "" | Exit survey

Dear participant, thank you for joining the xxx Webinar !

Please fill this short questionnaire in with your opinions and experience of the session: your feedback is extremely important for us to monitor and constantly improve the quality of our raising awareness and webinars' offer throughout the upcoming year.s We promise it won't take much of your time.

mariagiovanna.zamburlini@smartvenice.org [Cambia account](#)

Non condiviso

* Indica una domanda obbligatoria

1. Did you learn what you expected to during this webinar? *

- Yes, very much
- Yes
- Rather not
- Not at all

Avanti

Pagina 1 di 3

Cancella modulo

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Non condiviso

* Indica una domanda obbligatoria

2. How satisfied are you with the following aspects of the session? *

	Yes, very much	Yes	Rather not	Not at all
Relevance for your work/advocacy activities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Contents of the webinar	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Interactivity of the session	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

3. Are you satisfied with the use of the online platform in use? *

- Yes, very much
- Yes
- Rather not
- Not at all

4. Are you satisfied with the webinars' speakers? *

	Yes, very much	Yes	Rather not	Not at all
Knowledge of the topics	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Communication skills	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Use of gender+ sensitive language	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Listening and dialoguing attitudes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

5. As far as methods and approaches are concerned, did the session provide you with: *

	Yes, very much	Yes	Rather not	Not at all
Enough room to interact and participate	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge and tools suitable to be put in practice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Opportunities to reflect on your own beliefs/behaviours	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quality and accessibility of documentation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Equipment and technical support	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Timing/breaks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

6. Overall, are you satisfied with this session? *

- Yes
- Partly
- No

7. What was more or less interesting and convincing in the training and how could it be further improved (content-wise or methodologically, or both)? Any other comments/inputs on the webinar?

La tua risposta

Indietro

Avanti

Pagina 2 di 3

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Your profile

8. Your field of work

- AI/Computer sciences
- HR
- Human Rights
- Workers' rights
- Minorities rights
- Gender Equality

9. You identify as

- Woman
- Man
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say
- Prefer to describe, below

if you opted for "Prefer to describe" in Q.9, please provide a short answer here

La tua risposta

Indietro

Invia

Pagina 3 di 3

Cancella modulo

9.3 Slide-sets Screenshot⁷

9.3.1 Slide set for the course AI expert's course

9.3.2 Slide set for the HR specialist's course

9.3.3 Slide set for the course targeting worker's Representatives/NGOs

Identity Wheel: design by LOBA

⁷ Full slides show will be available after second roll-out session.

10 References

1. [Ponce del Castillo The AI Board Game, ETUI](#), 2023.
2. Donabedian framework, [GE Academy Horizon 2020 Project](#), 1966.
3. [Envisioning cards. A Value Sensitive Design Toolkit](#), 2020.
4. [FINDHR Project e-learning course](#), 2024.
5. [John Hopkins University, Integrative Learning and Life Design](#), 2024.
6. [Hiring Black Box](#), 2024.
7. [H2020 GE Academy Project](#), 2019-2021.
8. [Macdonald & Sánchez-Casal, 2002; hooks](#), 1994
9. [Ali M., Sapienzynski P. et al.'s paper on discrimination through optimization](#), 2019.
10. [SCHUFA Holding \(Scoring\) Case C-634/21, Judgment - 07/12/2023](#).

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email

info@biasproject.eu

website

www.biasproject.eu

social media

[@BIASProjectEU](https://twitter.com/BIASProjectEU)

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